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THE NOVEL CORONA VIRUS IN THE DYNAMICS OF THE INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM: DISRUPTIONS AND CONNECTIONS

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Abstract

As a novel actor of International Relations, SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) has created major upshots on the evolution of the contemporary International System: In the level of International Health (the WHO and States have been in discord and continuous verbal fracas); in terms of the International Economy (the economic crisis, the recession, etc.); on the aspect of International Security (increased activity of non-state armed groups); and finally, in terms of the ambience of international society, it creates a new competition: the Vaccine Race. This paper examines and discusses these numerous facets and impacts of COVID19 on the international society and concludes that the novel virus, far from being just flu”, has created fundamental alterations of disruptions and connections in the international society.

Key Words: Corona Virus, International Relations, Vaccine Race, Competition

INTRODUCTION

It has been assumed that international relations (IR) consist of the relations between states. But such a definition of world politics has been increasingly challenged since the late 1960s and the early 1970s, as many other non-state actors have become more and more involved in the international political process. As a result, transnational relations permeate world politics in almost every issue-area in which state and non-state actors interact regularly across national boundaries. The globalizing and liberalizing forces in the last three decades of the twentieth century have fundamentally transformed the structure of the world economy, thereby undermining the ability of states to govern. These great global transformations have influenced and modified the traditional paradigm and theories of IR, particularly the realist school of thought because of its basic premises that actors are states, and states operate in a system of anarchy.

Transnational relations, according to Thomas Risse-Kappen (1995: 172), are regular interactions across national boundaries involving at least one non-state actor or when such an actor does not operate in the interest of a national government or an intergovernmental organization. It is no exaggeration to say, as he claims, that transnational relations in this sense permeate world politics in almost all issue-areas. IR captures a vast array of themes ranging from the growing interconnectedness of people to old and new forms of security, dialogue and conflict between visions, beliefs and ideologies, the environment, space, the global economy, poverty and climate change. The sheer number of actors and issues that are relevant to IR can be overwhelming and are incessantly evolving with the times and tides. Covid-19 is an infectious disease caused by a

novel corona virus (nCoV), officially named as SARS-CoV-2 has become one of them.

The Coronavirus outbreak became global in January 2020, in the Chinese City of Wuhan, in the province of Hubei. The common symptoms of the virus are cold with fever, cough and difficulty in breathing. This new emerging virus novel Coronavirus (nCoV-2019) is a new strain but similar to earlier viruses such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS). The ongoing COVID-19 Pandemic is a crisis on a global scale that is currently affecting nations, international bodies, and citizens everywhere. Covid-19 has caused considerable morbidity and taken a heavy toll of lives.

The fact that the Coronavirus is not tied to any particular region nor grants immunity to nations with high GDP and HDI ratings does awake images of a World War One “Homefront” mentality, an era in which most of the dominant theories and perspectives in the field of International Relations took root and solidified. Months after the emergence of the worst global health crisis in a century the race is on to find the medical equivalent of the Holy Grail—a COVID-19 vaccine.

This paper seeks to clearly show the processes through which COVID19 alters the international system as it emerges as the newest actor in IR (Part I) and its afferent creation: the vaccine race (Part II). In each level of analysis, we shall clearly elaborate in a detailed form the several confrontations amongst state actors and how these confrontations affect the *modus operandi* of the international society, multilateralism and international security. Our task shall dwell on the scrutiny of COVID19 as a new actor of IR through its impact on the dynamics of

the contemporary international system: International security, inter-state relations, etc. and on how the pandemic solidifies the global capitalist assertions of demand and supply (as shown in the scramble for sanitary supplies).

I. COVID19: A NOVEL ACTOR OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected international relations and caused diplomatic tensions, as well as resulted in a United Nations Security Council resolution demanding a global ceasefire (UNSC, S/RES/2532). The diplomatic relations have been affected much due to the tensions around trade and transport of medicines, diagnostic tests and hospital equipment for the corona virus disease. Leaders of some countries have accused other countries for not containing the disease effectively and resulting in the uncontrolled spread of the virus. Developing nations in Latin America and Africa cannot find enough materials for testing for corona virus disease, partly because other countries in Europe and the United States and outspending the resources. In the bid to demonstrate the major disruptions caused by COVID19 to the international system, we shall examine the international impacts of the pandemic in three key themes: the impact of covid19 on International Peace, Security and Conflicts; covid19 as the new cold war battle-line between the United States and China; and the scramble for sanitary supplies: how the rich kill the poor.

A.) The impact of covid19 on International Peace, Security and Conflicts

In December 2019, when the novel strain of coronavirus first hit the headlines, 12 countries in the world were experiencing organized violence on an extensive scale, with more than 100 incidents of violence and attacks against

civilians recorded in that month (Pavlik, 2020: Accessed 5/11/2020). To most of these countries, the virus seemed a distant threat at the time. Yet, a few months and over 7 million recorded Covid-19 cases later, it has evolved from a distant threat to a stark reality. The global crisis – which has unleashed an emergency in the world’s public health, political, and economic systems simultaneously (Homer-Dixon, 1991: 79) – has subjected even the most stable societies to unprecedented disruption. In conflict-affected countries, i.e. countries with ongoing conflicts or a high risk of relapse into conflict, and countries emerging from conflicts, the pandemic has added another layer on top of often multiple existing layers of crisis.

On March 23, the UN Secretary General António Guterres made an unprecedented call for a global ceasefire. The call gained broad political support and encouraged hopes that the pandemic might serve as a catalyst for a cessation of armed hostilities. Nevertheless, if anything, a trend of intensifying conflicts and increased insecurity has been observed, as the pandemic responses have created opportunities for armed actors and left civilians more exposed to violence. In many conflict-affected countries, the weeks since the call have witnessed unabated or increased violence (Mustasilta, 2020: 2). Non-state armed groups in particular seem to have taken advantage of the global disruption to step up violent activities. In Westem Africa, for example, violence by non-state armed groups and militias was over 50% higher between 23 March and 25 April than the monthly average (Pavlik, 2020: Accessed 5/11/2020). Likewise, the so-called Islamic State has ramped up its activities in both Iraq and Syria (Cruickshank and Ressler, 2020: 4).

The increased activity of non-state armed groups reflects the broader effect of a power vacuum created by an external crisis (Ide et al., 2020: 4). The pandemic hits incumbent state authorities hard, as they face political pressures and responsibility to take drastic measures to combat the virus. Reallocation of resources and manpower (often military) can harm counterinsurgency efforts and weaken a state's capability to respond to armed challengers – unless it can rely on external support to avoid losing capacities (e.g. Libya). Armed groups, who do not face the same pressure to manage the crisis, are quick to seize the momentum to weaken their opponents (Columbo and Harris, Accessed on 10/08/2020). Aside from violent tactics, actors aiming at destabilizing the incumbent authorities can hinder or obstruct the state's response to the pandemic and/or act proactively and present themselves as more reliable alternatives – a tactic that may well work in the face of inadequate or unpopular policy measures. In internationalized conflicts (see the cases of Libya and Yemen), the extent to which armed actors are (or are not) constrained by the pandemic is contingent on the responses of their external allies.

There are three main ways in which the pandemic affects peace and conflict dynamics: the public health crisis, the policy responses to it, and the economic fallout arising from the coronavirus. Thus far, the pandemic has been accompanied by a rise in political violence around the world. Armed groups have capitalized on the crisis, while the global distraction caused by the pandemic has made it difficult to seize opportunities for peace. Clearly defined ceasefire frameworks, support towards local peace-builders, and the provision of substantive and long-term economic support in conflict-sensitive ways are crucial for

mitigating the risk of an escalatory spiral. Besides its impact on international conflict, covid19 has also become the new center stage for a war of rhetoric between China and the US.

A.) Covid19 as the new cold war battle-line between the United States and China

There is already a rich expert literature on the US-China trade war (Blustein, 2019; Lukin, 2019; Chong & Li, 2019; Accessed 9/8/2020). Mistrust and rivalry have been simmering between the US and China for years. However, since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, this has given way to open hostility: A "new Cold War"? This loaded term had already been floating in the air for some time, but on May 24 it was first used publicly by the Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi at the recent National People's Congress in Beijing. He was reacting to Washington's accusations that China was responsible for the global spread of the corona virus pandemic (FMPRC, 24th May 2020). Wang accused Washington of spreading "lies and conspiracy theories," telling journalists that in addition to the corona virus, there was a "political virus" running rampant in the United States.

The coronavirus has shifted sentiment in Washington in favor of a more severe decoupling of the US and Chinese economies than previously contemplated following the realization that US dependence on China extends to pharmaceuticals and medical equipment critical to combating the spread of the virus and maintaining public health (Huang, 2020: 6; Lee, 2020: 12). Early decouplers argued for a selective disengagement focusing on China's predatory economic practices, technologies with military application, and high value commercial IP and sensitive areas of the knowledge economy. But the gravity of the

coronavirus crisis has spurred talk in US policy circles of the need to consider a more extensive disentanglement of the US and Chinese economies and supply chains.

Hard decouplers, like Peter Navarro, have used the crisis to argue for greater economic self-reliance on public health and national security grounds, and a lessening of dependence on foreign markets, especially China. Navarro wants “to look strategically about moving supply chains on shore for essential medicines so that the American public is safe and the U.S. economy is secure” (Cassella, Accessed on 8/8/2020). Director of the US National Economic Council, Larry Kudlow, has floated the idea that the government could pay 100 percent of the removal costs of American firms willing to relocate manufacturing from China back to the US (Delaney, 2020).

The shift is also being driven by an increasingly vitriolic blame game about responsibility for the pandemic. Trump has unapologetically labeled COVID-19 as “the Chinese virus” and criticized Beijing for allowing it to get out of control. There have also been calls for China to pay reparations for the damage inflicted by the corona virus and for an international investigation to determine its origins and how it spread so rapidly. Chinese officials have struck back by suggesting that American soldiers visiting China were the initial source of the virus (Sherwell, 2020: 8). And China’s state media has once again drawn comparisons to the eight-nation alliance that put down the Boxer Rebellion and carved up the powers and territories of the Qing government while extracting reparations (Hess, 2020: Accessed 6/8/2020).

Some US hardliners view COVID-19 coordination with China as a “self-harming exercise in zero-sum competition for global leadership”, while their Chinese counterparts see

opportunities to advance the country's economic and geopolitical influence as foreigners look to invest in early recovered economies (Hass & Dong, 2020: Accessed 6/8/2020). They argue that China's ability to weather the pandemic's storm on its own proves that the country has nothing to fear from a decoupled world which may well occur on Beijing's terms. Apart from becoming a battle ground for a cold war theatre, the novel corona virus has also become a yardstick for economic inequality and a platform for the demonstration of global capitalism.

A.) The scramble for sanitary supplies: how the rich kills the poor.

As the United States and European Union countries compete to acquire scarce medical equipment to combat the corona virus, another troubling divide is also emerging in the international system, with poorer countries losing out to wealthier ones in the global scrum for masks and testing materials. Scientists in Africa and Latin America have been told by manufacturers that orders for vital testing kits cannot be filled for months, because the supply chain is in upheaval and almost everything they produce is going to America or Europe. All countries report steep price increases, from testing kits to masks. The huge global demand for masks, alongside new distortions in the private market, has forced some developing countries to turn to UNICEF for help. Eteleva Kadilli, who oversees supplies at the agency, said it was trying to buy 240 million masks to help 100 countries but so far had managed to source only around 28 million (Bradley, 2020: Accessed 7/8/2020).

The pandemic has had immediate and pronounced consequences in terms of medical supplies in the Commonwealth and globally. As countries tackle the virus,

there has been a significant spike in demand for diagnostic kits, critical medicines and artificial respiratory equipment like ventilators, as well as personal protective equipment (PPE) for frontline healthcare professionals. The scramble to acquire these essential medical goods has led to various unilateral trade measures – from curbing exports to eliminating import tariffs (Evenett, 2020; WTO, 2020) – as well as price wars and more extreme tactics, including allegations of ‘modern piracy’ as vital shipments are seized or contracts nullified. The disrupted production and supply of these goods, as well as global port closures and logistics hurdles, have led to difficulties meeting the increasing demand for medical supplies.

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought considerable attention to trade in medical products, and specifically trade in products for prevention, testing and treatment. The COVID-19 pandemic has spread to most countries and territories with hundreds of thousands of people infected, and a growing burden of fatalities. Understandably, governments are taking protective measures to stem the pandemic of the virus. Some of these measures may inadvertently impact the flow of critical medical goods across territories or might lead to breach of international trade contracts; for example, the seizure of 20 ventilators destined for Barbados by the US government in April 2020 (Smith, 2020: Accessed 8/8/2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic places Least Developed Countries (LDCs) in an extremely precarious position, given their high levels of economic and social vulnerability, fragile healthcare systems and limited preparedness to tackle the unfolding crisis. While the full impact of the pandemic, its duration and its aftereffects are still uncertain, it represents a significant blow to their

prospects for achieving many of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as well as a setback for countries expected to graduate from the LDC category. Amid the global scramble to secure supplies of medical goods, many governments are harnessing trade policy to help tackle the COVID-19 pandemic and bolster the effectiveness of their national health responses. They are doing so by curbing exports or easing imports. Several have also imposed nontariff measures that limit other countries' imports of COVID-19 related supplies and medical products (Evenett, 2020: 6).

One of the biggest disruptions to medical supply chains relates to port closures and global logistics hurdles. Around 80 per cent of global trade, including medical goods, is seaborne. To prevent the spread of the virus, a number of ports and shipping companies have implemented measures, including restrictions on the movement of professional seafarers and marine personnel. This is causing severe disruptions within the industry. It is therefore imperative to enhance trade facilitation and expedite customs procedures to keep vital goods moving as quickly as possible, especially the transit of essential medicine and equipment. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has proposed a number of measures to speed up the movement of goods at the border. These include reducing or minimizing physical interaction between officials and traders at the border; introducing regulations that enable the use of information and communication technologies to use e-payments, e-signatures and e-contracts; and relaxing cross-border data flow of sensitive information to monitor the epidemic (OECD, 2020: Accessed 8/8//2020).

I. THE COMPETITION OR RACE FOR A VACCINE

The assumption of competition among nation-states is a well-established premise of historical and sociological research on the modern state-system. The literature, however, typically focuses on certain forms of competition: States are seen as engaging in a continual power struggle for "hard" goods such as territories and natural and human resources while competition for "soft" ones such as attention, legitimacy, and the achievement of prestige tends to be neglected.

Since the global outbreak in early 2020, a wide range of researchers, backed by public and private funders, have rushed to accelerate R&D on vaccines and treatments. As a result, pre-clinical research and clinical trials have increased significantly. Hundreds of clinical trials have been registered since the beginning of 2020. Most of them test drug candidates but several vaccine candidates are also being tested. Testing many different approaches can increase the chances that at least one, or a few, candidates are successful.

Moscow researchers say one of the country's potential corona virus vaccines has been proven safe in small-scale human trials (Tass, 2020), and is ready for wider tests. It should be a modest win for a country that has sought for years to restore its Soviet-era reputation for cutting-edge science, and for President Vladimir Putin (Kremlin, 2020: Accessed 7/8/2020). Yet on Thursday, Britain, the U.S. and Canada accused Russia of hacking international research centers that are trying to develop a vaccine. The Kremlin denies any involvement, while the head of the country's sovereign wealth fund called the allegations an attempt to

tarnish the Russian research effort. It's still an accusation that jeopardizes a hoped-for inoculation boost for prestige.

A.) Science, politics and the race for a corona virus vaccine

The announcement Tuesday by Russian President Vladimir Putin that his country was the first to approve a corona virus vaccine did not provoke the awe and wonder of the Soviet Union's launch of the first satellite into orbit in 1957. Instead, it was met by doubts about the science and safety. But the claim underscored how, like the space race, the competition to have the first vaccine is about international rivalries as well as science. The first nation to develop a way to defeat the novel corona virus will achieve a kind of moon-shot victory and the global status that goes along with it. That's valuable to Putin, whose popularity at home has declined amid a stagnant economy and the ravages of the virus outbreak.

"To be the first one out of the block with a corona virus vaccine would be a real — pardon the pun — shot in the arm for the Kremlin," said Timothy Frye, a political science professor at Columbia University who specializes in post-Soviet politics. Russia is not alone in viewing a vaccine in this light. China, where the virus first emerged, has also raced to make progress on a vaccine. A state-owned Chinese company is boasting that its employees, including top executives, received experimental shots even before the government approved testing in people. U.S. President Donald Trump, whose handling of the corona virus pandemic has put his political fate in grave jeopardy, is hoping to get credit for his administration's aggressive push for a vaccine, ideally one that arrives before the

election in November. It's far from clear at this point whether Putin has beaten Trump to this medical milestone. It's also possible Russia had helped. The U.S., Britain and Canada last month accused hackers working for Russian intelligence of trying to steal information about a corona virus vaccine from academic and pharmaceutical research institutions. In any case, the public is eager for a vaccine as global deaths from the virus surpass 730,000. Some say they would even welcome one from Russia, provided it passes muster with the U.S. Food and Drug Administration, which approves vaccines used in the United States, and the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, which recommends who should receive them in the nation.

A.) The International Political Economy of Vaccines

The vaccine is a very special pharmaceutical product, not only medically - it is one of the very few primary preventive drugs - but also economically and socially, and even politically. The vaccine is both a product and a concept or, more precisely, it is the variation of a concept into a product.

Behind this frantic competition in search of the vaccine that would make it possible to get out of the pandemic crisis, an economic race is emerging. The United States has already spent 5.5 billion Euros, divided between different laboratories, to ensure the receipt of several million doses of the vaccines, which are still only candidate vaccines. Europe, through France, Germany, Italy and the Netherlands, was quick to react and disbursed 300 million Euros to pre-reserve 300 million doses for the British pharmaceutical industry AstraZeneca. The UK has also stepped in and spent more than 100 million Euros to ensure

it receives the necessary doses of vaccine. These staggering figures, which reflect an indirect form of research funding, are more of a “political strategy”, analyzes economist Nathalie Coutinet: “These pre-orders are used by pharmaceutical companies to allow them to adapt their production equipment to be able to quickly produce huge quantities of vaccines. Behind this, we see a political logic of states to tell their populations that they are able to meet their health requirements, as was the case with masks or beds in hospitals. ”

Industrially, the vaccine market, which is small (a little over 2% of the drug market) but dynamic and innovative, has been experiencing significant upheaval for several years. New concepts (so-called “therapeutic” vaccines) have thus emerged, new pathologies including the discovery of the infectious etiology of certain cancers, new production methods with recombinant vaccines. It's a fast-moving world. And public opinion, which is no contradiction, calls on researchers to develop vaccines against HIV infection or the Ebola virus.

Long considered a separate sector in the world of medicine, the vaccine has for several years undergone a process of “pharmacization” which affects both research and development and pre- and post-MA evaluation. For a long time, the evaluation criteria for vaccines were confined to simple in vitro tests of immunogenicity and safety. Today, “vaccine candidates” are the subject of pharmaceutical-type clinical development with phase III trials which, in some cases such as HPV, have involved thousands of patients.

For a long time, vaccines were produced by small specialized companies, more or less artisanal, more or less linked to public institutions, on the fringes of major industrial trends. Today, large international firms such as

Sanofi, GSK and Pfizer have made it a major focus of development.

For a long time, the vaccine received little public funding, especially in developing countries; today these funds are relayed by large international “facilities”, such as the GAVI alliance, which mobilize private and public funds to carry out mass vaccination campaigns against pathologies as varied as yellow fever, cholera, measles and mumps, hepatitis B, pneumococcal infection, etc. with often spectacular results.

CONCLUSION

The Covid-19 was originated from Wuhan city of China and spread all over the world. It is right that no one is safe from that. There are many political, economic, social, and religious myths on the origin of Covid-19. Pandemics are striking with greater frequency primarily because of deforestation, environmental degradation, rapid urbanization, overpopulation, migration and growing animal and human conflict. There is no herd or population immunity against new pathogens such as the Sars-Cov-2 that causes the corona virus disease (Covid-19), and till herd or population immunity crosses 70%, it will continue to spread. In these circumstances, public health interventions in combination with an effective vaccine may mitigate the situation. The speed with which the Covid-19 pandemic is progressing leaves the world with no choice but to have an emergency-use vaccine ready within six to eight months.

The spread of the Corona virus disease has revealed the fragility of health systems in all countries of the world both large and small. The measure of this pandemic in terms of financial allocations has been the most severe test facing

the world since the Great Depression in 1929. More so, its catastrophic effects on the global economy, on food supply, as well as its socio-cultural and general psychological trauma calls for the need to conduct a comprehensive review of international relations frameworks by focusing on global environmental cooperation to address future sanitary risks that the world may face.

It has become apparent that the repercussions of the corona virus disease have cast a shadow on the relations within the states in the International System. However, the Corona virus pandemic has re-modified the ethos of the international scene from multilateral cooperation to that of absolute competition which threatens the existence and future of inter-national- relations. Moving forward, what's at stake for inter-national-relations? Will the post-pandemic era become collide with the end of a multilateral international Society?

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